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IMPORTANCE OF MULTIMODAL ANALGESIA IN NUSS PROCEDURES IN CHILDREN- our experiences

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Introduction: Minimally invasive surgical techniques have increasingly been used to repair thoracic deformities. Perioperative anesthetic and pain management of patients undergoing the Nuss procedure is a challenge to the anesthesiologist. A general anesthesia with adequate analgesic technique is crucial for the success of the surgical procedure and for reducing perioperative complications.

Material and methods: The research was conducted as clinical retrospective study, it included patients operated with the Nuss technique at the Children's Surgery Clinic in Novi Sad, in the period from 2006 to 2021. The collected data were systematized and entered into an established database, and then statistically processed. Pain assesment was performed using a numerical pain scale.

Results: 36 patients aged 9 to 19 years participated in the research. Male gender appeared in a statistically significantly higher number. Anesthesia was maintained with general anesthesia using either remifentanyl + propofol - in 25 (65,8%) patients, or sevoflurane + remifentanyl - in 13 (34,2%) patients. Epidural anesthesia was performed in 9 patients (23,7%). Postoperative analgesia was achieved with epidural (chirocaine + fentanil) - 9 patients (23,7%) for 48h, or continuous remifentanil (0,05mcg / kg / min, for 24h-36h) in 29 patients (76,3%). All patients, after that period, received tramadol + NSAID. Pain score values were 2 – 4 in all patients. Average hospitalization for all patients was 8,6 days, with no difference regarding to type of analgesia.

Conclusion: NUSS operation is a very painful procedure performed quite frequently in adolescents. Continuous intraoperative and postoperative remifentanil infusion provides good analgesia and early mobilization of patients. Regional anesthesia was used in 9 patients with good but insufficient effect. The best analgesic for postoperative pain control was the opioid analgesic remifentanil in combination with systemic analgesics. Postoperative pain treatment requires use of multimodal analgesia.

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